

IPBES BBA Chapter 2 - Literature review / IPBES business and biodiversity assessment (2.1)

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https://ipbes-data.github.io/IPBES_BBA_Ch2_Snowball/snowball.html

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Description

This review is part of the methodological assessment of the impact and dependence of business on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people. Experts from Chapter 2, along with the technical support unit on data management, conducted a snowball search to gather literature on business dependencies on biodiversity. The aim was to collect information on how businesses depend on biodiversity and the methods used to measure this dependency. The process was structured into five phases: i) selection of key papers by Chapter 2 authors, ii) snowball search for additional references, iii) screening for inclusion and exclusion of references to be used, iv) structured literature review and v) analysis of results from the review.

Process Overview

Protocol

- i. **Type of analysis/search/review:** Selection of key papers identified through expert selection
 - **Search languages:** English
 - **Search engine:** Each author independently searched and selected for two or three key papers on business dependencies on biodiversity.
 - **Search Dates:** September 25, 2023, to October 13, 2023
 - **Sample extracted:** 20 key articles published between 2012 and 2023
 - **Location and format of data:** [IPBES BBA 2.1 07-2024 \(A\)](#)

- ii. **Type of analysis/search/review:** Snowball search for articles indexed in [OpenAlex.org](#).
 - **Search languages:** Not relevant, as all papers citing the key papers and cited by the key papers were identified, regardless of their language. All papers in the OpenAlex corpus were included, irrespective of language.
 - **Search engine:** Open Alex
 - **Search date:** October 23 2023
 - **Location and format of data:** [IPBES_BBA_2.1_07-2024_\(B\)](#)
 - **Sample extracted:** On October 23 2023, the data management TSU using the 20 key articles(A) conducted a snowball search and found 1934 papers (B) relevant (additional information can be found on the following link: [IPBES BBA Ch2 Snowball](#))

- iii. **Type of analysis/search/review:** Initial screening for inclusion of relevant references.
 - **Treatment applied:** From the 1934 papers, we examined only articles in English language and with the following two key aspects, i) Does the article address one or more ISIC categories? and ii) Is there a link between business and biodiversity in the article (yes/no/unsure)? Using these questions, the authors assessed the relevance of the articles from the snowball search. Even if a paper was initially assessed as not having a clear link between biodiversity and business, it could still be deemed relevant in this initial screening. As a result, 484 articles were selected as relevant publications. These articles were then subjected to a more detailed screening process later.

The 484 references identified as relevant were included in the structured literature review template (R1). The references were then evenly divided among the experts in Chapter 2 for a detailed structured literature review.
 - **Sample extracted:** 484 records marked as included
 - **Location and format of the data:** [IPBES BBA 2.1 07-2024 \(R1\)](#).

- iv. **Type of analysis/search/review:** Detailed screening for inclusion of relevant references
 - **Treatment applied:** We conducted a second screening of literature review. A template was developed among Chapter 2 members (R1). The template formulates information

categories to meet the information needs of the different sections of the chapter. A detailed list of the final categories, their descriptions and answer options are provided in (C).

- It is important to remark that the response options for methods were based on methods classification used in IPBES Methodological assessment of the diverse values and valuation of nature, which the chapter experts used to create a shorter classification with seven categories as response options. For the other categories, the response option categories were based on experts' judgment.
- To ensure consistent interpretation of the categories and their response options among the experts, we selected three articles for all experts to read and complete the template in a joint meeting, any ambiguities in the categories and their response options were discussed, and the template was finalized.
- During the interpretation process, we decided to include a more detailed criterion for inclusion/exclusion. For a reference to be considered relevant, it needed to fulfill the following criteria:
 - The reference assesses a business dependency on nature's contributions to people, ecosystem services, or biodiversity.
 - AND
 - The reference presents original work (not a review or meta-analysis), i.e., uses primary data or presents a new analysis of secondary data.
 - The reference uses empirical data (qualitative or quantitative).
 - The reference is accessible and in a language that one of the Chapter 2 authors can understand.
- As a result, 151 references were selected to be included in the analysis. These references can be found on column F of the Structured literature review template (R1)
- **Sample extracted:** 151 papers used for the literature review
- **Location and format of the data:** [IPBES_BBA_2.1_07-2024_\(R1\)](#)

v. **Analysis of results from the detailed screening**

Based on the 151 references identified in the detailed screening, we first assessed the valuation methods used to measure dependencies. A detailed description of these methods is provided in section 2.3

The magnitude of the dependencies was often reported across (i) multiple ISIC subsectors (see R4 for the crop to ISIC classification), (ii) different measurement units, and (iii) different countries. Based on this, we created two sub-sets of references: one with 53 articles covering various ISIC subsectors, and another with 66 articles reporting different measurement units for dependencies.

From the 66-article sub-set, we grouped the reported units into four main categories. These classifications (R6) are shown in Table 2.6 of Chapter 2, while the number of papers per ecosystem service is shown in (R2).

For the 53 article sub-set, we examined which ISIC crop subcategories had been studied in relation to pollination and water quantity services. Using the classifications in (R5), we calculated their frequencies and represented them as percentages in heatmaps (Figure 2.5, Chapter 2).

In addition, we drew from data from one paper to illustrate the dependency of different crops in Brazil on pollination services (Figure 2.2) using their corresponding ISIC subcategory based on (R4). Finally, Figure 2.9 presents the regional distribution of dependency studies, based on the classifications derived during the detailed review (R1).

It is important to note that the literature review did not follow a systematic search protocol. Instead, it relied on snowball sampling, meaning that the results are inevitably influenced by the set of 20 articles initially selected.

Additional files

ID	Name	File Type	Size (KB)	Description
A	IPBES_BBA_2.1_0-7_2024_(A)	PDF	170 KB	Initial list of 20 papers selected for the snowballing literature search.
B	IPBES_BBA_2.1_0-7_2024_(B)	XLS	1548 KB	Sample extracted of 1934 articles on October 23 2023.
C	IPBES_BBA_2.1_2024_(C)	PDF	216 KB	Description of the categories of the review template used for the detailed screening.
R1	IPBES_BBA_2.1_0-7_2024_(R1)	XLS	680 KB	Structured literature review template. It includes the result of 151 articles used during the literature review.
R2	IPBES_BBA_2.1_0-7_2024_(R2)	PDF	89 KB	Number of subsampled papers identifying various measurements of dependencies
R3	IPBES_BBA_2.1_2024_(R3)	PDF	121 KB	Categories of the template for the magnitude extraction data.
R4	IPBES_BBA_2.1_2024_(R4)	PDF	130 KB	Crops with their corresponding ISIC subcategories
R5	IPBES_BBA_2.1_2024_(R5)	PDF	115 KB	Main unit types to measure dependencies.
R6	IPBES_BBA_2.1_2024_(R6)	PDF	119 KB	Template to group the studies under different ecosystem services dependencies categories and the sectors that received the benefits.

